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ABSTRACT

Arthroscopic diagnosis in meniscal injuries and demonstrating the advantages of arthroscopic meniscectomy.

During the year, 429 patients with various injuries of the meniscus of the knee joint were observed in the Department of Large Orthopedics of the Samarkand Branch of the Republican Specialized Traumatology Scientific-Practical Medical Center of Orthopedics (STSPMCO). All of these underwent arthroscopic meniscectomy.

Of these, 269 (62.7%) were men and 160 (37.3%) were women. The right knee meniscus was 254 (59.2%), the left knee meniscus was 110 (25.6%) and both knees. menisci were 65 (15.2%). Depending on the type of damage: watering can handle 136 (31.7%), longitudinal 122 (28.4%), clotted type 114 (26.6%), horizontal type 57 (13.3). damage to the peripheral part was 324 (75.5%) and damage to the central part was 165 (24.5%).

According to our research, 94% of the results are excellent and show good results - the method of diagnosis and treatment of meniscal injuries using arthroscopy is highly effective, less traumatic to the internal elements of the joint, clearly shows pathology, does not keep the patient in the hospital, activates the patient faster and achieves relatively good results.

Keywords: Knee joint, meniscus, meniscectomy, medial meniscus, lateral meniscus, arthroscopy.

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РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ АРТРОСКОПИЧЕСКОЙ ПАРЦИАЛЬНОЙ МЕНИСКЭКТОМИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Артроскопическая диагностика повреждений мениска и демонстрация преимуществ артроскопической менискэктомии.

В Самаркандском филиале Республиканского специализированного травматологического-ортопедического научно-практического медицинского центра (СФРНПМЦТиО) в течение года наблюдали 429 больных с различными повреждениями мениска коленного сустава. Всем им была выполнена артроскопическая менискэктомия.

Из них мужчин было 269 (62,7%), женщин – 160 (37,3%), мениска правого колена – 254 (59,2%), мениска левого колена – 110 (25,6%), мениска обоих колен – 65 (15,2%). В зависимости от вида повреждения: Ручка-лейка 136 (31,7%), продольное 122 (28,4%), тромбозное 114 (26,6%), горизонтальное 57 (13,3), повреждение периферического отдела 324 (75,5%) и повреждение центральной части составило 165 (24,5%).

По нашим исследованиям 94% результатов отличные и показывают хорошие результаты - метод диагностики и лечения повреждений мениска с помощью артроскопии высоко эффективен, малотравматичен для внутренних элементов сустава, четко показывает патологию, не сохраняет пациента в больнице, быстрее активизирует пациента и достигает относительно хороших результатов.

Ключевые слова: Коленный сустав, мениск, менискэктомия, внутренний мениск, наружный мениск, артроскопия,

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ARTROSKOPIK PARSIAL MENISKEKTOMIYANING NATIJALARI**ANNOTATSIYA**

Menisklarning jarohatlarida artroskopik diagnostika va artroskopik meniskektomiyaning afzalliklarini ko‘rsatishdan iborat.

Respublika ixtisoslashtirilgan travmatologiya ortopediya ilmiy - amaliy tibbiyot markazi Samarqand filialining (RITOIATMSF) Yirik bo‘g‘imlar ortopediyasi bo‘limida bir yil davomida 429 ta bemorlar tizza bo‘g‘imi menisklarini har xil jarohatlari bilan kuzatildi. Bularning barchasi artroskopik meniskektomiya qilingan.

Bularning 269 (62,7%) tasini erkaklar, 160 (37,3%) tasini ayollar tashkil qildilar. O‘ng tizza bo‘g‘imi menisklari 254 (59,2%), chap tizza bo‘g‘imi menisklari 110(25,6%) tani va ikkala tizza menisklari 65(15,2%) tashkil qilgan. Zararlanish turlariga qarab: ruchka- leyka 136(31,7%) tani, uzunasiga 122(28,4%), laxtaksimom tipda 114 (26,6%) tani, gorizontal turi 57 (13,3) tani tashkil qildilar. O‘rnashgan o‘rniga karab, periferik qismini zararlanishi 324(75,5%) tani, markaziy kismini zararlanishi esa 165(24,5%) tani tashkil qildi.

Bizning izlanishlarimiz bo‘yicha 94% a‘lo va yaxshi natijalar olingan. Bu natijalar shuni ko‘rsatadiki menisklar jarohatini artroskop yordamida tashxis qo‘yish va davolari yuqori effektli, bo‘g‘im ichki elementlarini kam jarohatlovchi, patologiyani aniq ko‘rsatuvchi, bemorni shifoxonada uzoq ushlaymaydigan, bemorni tezroq aktivlashtiruvchi va nisbatan yaxshi natija oladigan davolash va diagnostic metodidir.

Kalit so‘zlar: Tizza bo‘g‘imi, menisk, meniskektomiya, medial menisk, lateral menisk, artroskopiya.

Menisklarning jarohati tizza bo‘g‘imi ichi elementlari zararlanishlari orasida birinchi o‘rinda turadi va bu esa tizza bo‘g‘imini mo‘tadil ishlashini keskin buzadi [5,8].

Tizza bo‘g‘imida medial va lateral menisklar farqlanadi. Medial menisk 80%-90%, lateral menisk esa 10-20% hollarda jarohatlanadi. Bu holat tizza bo‘g‘imini o‘ziga xos anatomik tuzilishi bilan, ya‘ni medial menisk bo‘g‘im xaltasi, bog‘lamalar yordamida birikib, jarohatlanish jarayonida

kam harakatchan bo‘ladi va jarohatni ko‘p qismini o‘z ichiga oladi. Menisklar to‘g‘ridan - to‘g‘ri ya‘ni, bevosita hamda bilvosita mexanizmdan jarohatlanishi mumkin. Lekin jarohatlanishning hamma mexanizmlarida ham, tizza bo‘g‘imi keskin buralib, oyoqqa kuchli tiralish holati bo‘lishi kerak.

Menisklarni jarohatini tasnifida ularning o‘rni va jarohat shakliga qarab ajratiladi.

Menisklar jarohatini o‘tkir davrida aniqlash qiyin bo‘ladi chunki bu davrda qattiq og‘riq, gemartroz va tizzada harakat qiyin bo‘ladi. Tizza bo‘g‘imida jarohatni surunkali davrida 3 ta sindromal guruh ajratiladi [1,3,7].

- 1) Og‘riq simptomlari.
- 2) Yallig‘lanish – distrofik simptomlari.
- 3) Tizzada harakatni buzilish simptomlari.

Bularni hammasini ham birga uchratish juda qiyin. Radiologik tekshirish metodlaridan albatta, bemorlarni hammasiga ham ikki proyeksiyada (oldingi –orqa va yonbosh) rentgenogramma qilinishi kerak. Rentgenogrammada tizza bo‘g‘imini boshqa og‘irroq jarohatlarini (sinish, chiqish) aniqlab bo‘ladi. Lekin bu metod bilan menisklar jarohatini aniqlab bo‘lmaydi, chunki menisklar o‘zlarida rentgen nurlarini saqlay olmaydi. Buning uchun tizza bo‘g‘imi ichiga havo yoki kontrast moddalar kiritish kerak. Shundayam menisklar zararlanishini aniqlash qiyin bo‘ladi. Keyingi vaqtlarda menisklar jarohatlari diagnostikasida UZI, MRT va artroskopiya kabi diagnostika usullari qo‘llanilayapti [1,4].

MRT – kam invaziv yaxshi usul bo‘lishi bilan birga qimmat turadigan va 100 foiz hamma vaqt ham menisk zararlanishini aniqlab bo‘lmaydi. Ko‘pchilik olimlarning fikri bo‘yicha bu metod 83-90% gacha natija berishi mumkin [6].

Ortopediyaning rivojlanishining hozirgi davrida faqat artroskopiyagina yaxshi tekshirish va davolash usuli bo‘lishi mumkin [2].

Tadqiqot maqsadi: Menisklarning jarohatlarida artroskopik diagnostika va artroskopik meniskektomiyaning afzalliklarini ko‘rsatishdan iborat.

Tadqiqot materiallari va usullari. Respublika ixtisoslashtirilgan travmatologiya ortopediya ilmiy - amaliy tibbiyot markazi Samarqand filialining (RITOIATMSF) Yirik bo‘g‘imlar ortopediyasi bo‘limida bir yil davomida 429 ta tizza bo‘g‘imi menisklarini har xil jarohatlari bilan bemorlar kuzatildi. Bularning 269 (62,7%) tasini erkaklar, 160 (37,3%) tasini ayollar tashkil qildilar.

O‘ng tizza bo‘g‘imi menisklari 254 (59,2%), chap tizza bo‘g‘imi menisklari 110 (25,6%) tani va ikkala tizza menisklari 65 (15,2%) tani tashkil qilgan.

Zararlanish turlariga qarab: ruchka- leyka 136 (31,7%) tani, uzunasiga 122 (28,4%), laxtaksimom tipda 114 (26,6%) tani, gorizontali turi 57 (13,3) tani tashkil qildilar. O‘rnashgan o‘rniga qarab, periferik qismini zararlanishi 324 (75,5%) tani, markaziy qismini zararlanishi esa 165 (24,5%) tani tashkil qildi. Meniskni periferik qism bilan yaxshi ta‘minlangan bo‘ladi.

30 yoshgacha bo‘lgan bemorlar soni boshqa yoshdagilarga nisbatan ko‘pni, ya‘ni 249 (58%) ni tashkil qildilar, chunki bu yoshdagilar ko‘proq harakatchan va sportni ko‘proq oyoqqa zo‘riqish beradigan turi bilan shug‘ullanadilar, 30-45 yoshgacha bo‘lgan bemorlar 124 (29%) tani, 45-59 yoshdagilar 51 (12%) tani va 60-74 yoshdagilar esa 5 (1%) tani tashkil qildilar. Artroskopik diagnostika maqsadida 18 (4,2%) ta bemorlarda, qolgan bemorlarda 411 (95,8%) ham diagnostika ham davolash artroskopiyasi qilindi, 6 (1,4%) bemorlarda menisk qattiq zararlangani uchun total artroskopik meniskektomiya, boshqalarida 423 (98,6%) tasida esa parsial meniskektomiya o‘tkazildi.

Bemorlar maxsus tayyorgarlikdan keyin operatsiyaga olindi va orqa miya anesteziyasi ostida, ko‘rsatmasiga qarab total yoki parsial meniskektomiya qilindi.

Operatsiyadan 1 kun o‘tgandan keyin oyoqqa zo‘riqish bermay, qo‘ltiq tayoqlar yordamida yurishga ruxsat berildi. Bir oygacha oyoqqa qattiq bosmay yurishga va 2 oydan keyin mehnat faoliyati tiklandi. Sport bilan shug‘ullanadiganlarga 6 oydan keyin zo‘riqish bilan yurishga ruxsat berildi. Artroskopiyaning yana bir yaxshi tomoni meniskni zararlanishi aniq tashxisi bilan birga, bo‘g‘imni boshqa patologiyalari ham diagnostika qilindi va ko‘rsatmasiga qarab davolandi. Artroskopiya vaqtida menisk zararlanishi bilan birga kechayotgan artrit 84 (14,6%) ta, revmatoid artrit 12 (2,8%) tasida, sinoviallar 16 (3,7%) tasida kuzatildi va ular ko‘rsatmasi qarab davolash muolajalarini oldilar.

Artroskopiya yordamida tizzada patologiya aniqlanib davolash muolajalari aniq shu patologiyaga qaratiladi va buning natijasida tizza bo‘g‘imida boshqa strukturalari jarohat olmaydi.

Artroskopiya vaqtida bo‘g‘imni boshqa strukturalari zararlanishlari bo‘lsa yoki zararlangan meniskni artroskop yordamida meniskektomiya qiyin bo‘lsa miniartrotomiya qilinib zararlangan strukturalar olib tashlandi.

O‘z ish faoliyatimizdan klinik misollar keltiramiz:

Rasm 1. Bemor K.M. 1996y. Kas.tar №186. Operatsiyadan oldin: O‘ng tizza bo‘g‘imi ichki meniski “ruchka – leyka” tipida jarohati.

Rasm 2. Bemor K.M. 1996y. Kas.tar №186 Operatsiyadan keyin: Artroskopik total meniskektomiya.

Rasm 3. Bemor T.S., 1991y. Kas.tar №174 operatsiyadan oldin: O‘ng tizza bo‘g‘imi ichki meniski laxtaksim tipida eskirgan jarohati.

Rasm 4. Bemor T.S., 1991y. Kas.tar №174 operatsiyadan keyin: Artroskopik parsial meniskektomiya o‘tkazilgan

Artroskop yordamida tizza bo‘g‘imida o‘tkazilgan menisklar jarohati diagnostikasi va davolash usulining natijalarini quyidagidek baholadik:

297 (69%) ta bemorda a‘lo natijalar kuzatildi. Bunda bemorlar og‘riqsiz, yaxshi yuradilar, tizza bo‘g‘imida harakat chegaralanmagan, bo‘g‘imda shish yo‘q va mehnat faoliyati tiklangan.

103 (24%) tasida yaxshi natija qayd qilindi- Bular yaxshi yuradilar lekin kunni oxirida, ko‘p yurganda, havo bulutli, yomg‘irli bo‘lganda bo‘g‘imda biroz og‘riqni sezadilar, shish yo‘q, bo‘g‘imda harakat chegaralanmagan.

23 (59%) tasida natija qoniqarli deb topildi. Bular ko‘p yurgan kuni havo bulutli yomg‘irli bo‘lgan kuni og‘riq sezadilar, tizzada faol harakat 5-10⁰ gacha chegaralangan.

6 (1,5%) ta bemorda davolash natijasini qoniqarsiz deb hisobladik- bularda kunni oxiriga borib tizza bo‘g‘imi shishadi, og‘rik sezadilar, bo‘g‘imda deformatsiyali artroz, tizza bo‘g‘imida harakat chegaralangan va mehnat faoliyati tiklanmagan. Qoniqarsiz natijalar, asosan, operatsiyagacha

bo'g'imda deformatsiyali artroz, sinovit bo'lgan bemorlar, operatsiyadan keyingi rejimni buzganlarda va keksalarda kuzatildi.

Yuqorida ko'rsatilgan 94% yaxshi natijalar menisklar jarohatini artroskop yordamida davolash yaxshi usul ekanini yana bir bor tasdiqlaydi.

Artroskop orqali parsial meniskektomiya usuli yuqori effektli, kam jarohatli, patologiyaning o'ziga ta'sir o'tkazishi, bemorni tez harakat qildiruvchi, shifoxonada davolash muddatini qisqartiruvchi va mehnat faoliyatini tezda tiklovchi usuldir.

Xulosalar. 1. Bizning kuzatishimiz bo'yicha bo'limda davolangan bemorlarning 32% i tizzalar meniskining zararlanishi bilan davolanganligi shuni ko'rsatadiki bu patologiya tizza bo'g'imini ichki strukturasi jarohatlanishi o'rtasida birinchi o'rinda turadi.

2. Bizning izlanishlarimiz bo'yicha 94% a'lo va yaxshi natijalar olingan- shuni ko'rsatadiki menisklar jarohatini artroskop yordamida tashxis qo'yish va davolari yuqori effektli, bo'g'im ichki elementlarini kam jarohatlovchi, patologiyani aniq ko'rsatuvchi, bemorni shifoxonada uzoq ushlaymaydigan, bemorni tezroq aktivlashtiruvchi va nisbatan yaxshi natija oladigan davolash va diagnostik metodidir.

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